

SPATIAL PREFILTERING OF INTERFERENCE SOURCES USING
SUBARRAYS OF REACTIVELY STEERED ADAPTIVE ARRAYS

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INTRODUCTION - A reactively steered adaptive array (RESAA) contains a single element connected by transmission line to a receiver. A number of parasitic elements are located in close proximity to this driven element, and each is terminated in an adjustable reactive load. The pattern is formed by adjustment of these loads to steer nulls toward sources of interference.

Recent studies [1,2] of this technique have shown that it performs well when the number of controlled reactive loads is relatively low (eight is the maximum feasible number) and the element spacing is small (about 0.15λ ; λ is wavelength). The compactness of the resulting array suggests the application of the RESAA technique shown in Fig. 1. The subarrays, phase shifters, and summer form a conventional phased array structure, but each subarray is an independent RESAA. In effect, the volume normally occupied by a single element in the phased array is broken up into a driven element and its reactively loaded parasitics. The RESAAs thus function as a prefilter to remove unwanted power from the strongest two or three interference sources before this power reaches the phase shifters, summer, receiver, and other components of finite dynamic range.

In this paper, we present the results of a simulation of the array in Fig. 1. As in earlier studies of RESAAs [1,2], extensive simulations are necessary because of the difficulty in deriving an analytical expression for the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio.

THEORY AND SIMULATION DETAILS - We assume an array of five subarrays, with each subarray separated by $d = 0.5\lambda$. We call this the primary array to avoid confusion with the subarrays. The elements of the primary array are disposed along the x-axis (Fig. 1). The pattern of the primary array is formed by the phase-shifted uniformly weighted outputs of each subarray according to the standard array factor equation:

$$G(\hat{r}) = \sum_{n=0}^{N_s-1} e^{jk(\hat{r} - \hat{r}_b) \cdot \vec{r}'_n}, \quad (1)$$

where N_s is the number of subarrays; \hat{r} and \hat{r}_b the unit vectors in polar coordinates to the pattern observation point and desired beam position, respectively; \vec{r}'_n the coordinate vector for the nth element; and $k = 2\pi/\lambda$. We define the azimuth plane as the x-z plane and the elevation plane as the y-z plane.

Each subarray has the configuration shown in the inset of Fig. 1. Each element is a resonant half-wave dipole, with a separation between elements of 0.5λ along the y-axis and 0.1λ along the x-axis. The array factor for this array is given by [1]

$$H(\hat{r}) = g(\hat{r}) \sum_{n=1}^{N_e} \{ [Z_A + Z_L]^{-1} \}_{n1} e^{jk\hat{r} \cdot \hat{r}'_{on}} \quad , \quad (2)$$

where $g(\hat{r})$ is the dipole element pattern, $\{ \dots \}_{n1}$ the $n1$ element of the enclosed matrix, 1 the index for the driven element, \hat{r}'_{on} the coordinate vector for the n th element, $[Z_A]$ the array impedance matrix, and $[Z_L]$ a diagonal matrix of the reactive loads. The total array output is then given by $F(\hat{r}) = G(\hat{r})H(\hat{r})$. For the simulations, the entries in $[Z_A]$ were computed using a method of moments program.

As set up here, the primary array is a linear array designed to steer a beam in the azimuth (x-z) plane, with planar RESAAs capable of steering nulls in both the azimuth and elevation planes. We have also studied several other configurations, including planar primary arrays and larger subarrays, which will not be discussed.

Several different schemes for implementing the subarray control can be formulated, but we have concentrated on the method in Fig. 1. Only a single adaptive processing loop is required that operates on the output of any one of the subarrays. The reactive loads are then copied into the RESAA subarrays on the remaining elements. The control algorithm used in the simulations is the same optimum gradient algorithm discussed in [1,2]. One or two interferers and a desired signal were incident on the array.

RESULTS - The results of a typical run are shown in Figs. 2-4. Figure 2 is an elevation-azimuth contour plot of the adapted subarray pattern for the case of interference incident from $(-85,0)$ and $(0,45)$. A beam is desired at $(45,0)$, and the beam coordinates are input to the adaptive nulling algorithm. Figure 3 shows a contour plot of the adapted pattern for the primary array. Nulls are formed toward both interference sources that are at least -36 dB below the beam response at $(45,0)$.

Shown in Fig. 4 is a cut in the azimuth plane at elevation = 0, taken from Figs. 2 and 3. The beam at $(45,0)$ and the suppression of the interference at $(-85,0)$ are evident. For comparison, the pattern for the primary array with unity element factors is also shown (i.e., the resulting pattern if each RESAA subarray were replaced with a single dipole). The interference at $(-85,0)$ is observed to be reduced by 30 dB by the subarray.

Some general observations noted from simulations to date are the following:

1. The particular five-element RESAA subarray described here could form a distinct null towards a single interferer at any elevation and azimuth. Two interferers could be nulled as long as both interferers were not incident in the same principal plane (i.e., the $x=0$ plane or the $y=0$ plane in Fig. 1). Three interferers could not all be nulled, since there is an insufficient number of degrees of freedom [2].

2. The "load copy" step in Fig. 1 is a source of error because the reactance characteristics of the loads in each subarray have to be known. Errors of up to 5% or so are tolerable (a small effect on the nulling capability), but keeping errors within this bound may be difficult in practical hardware.

3. An alternative is to provide each RESAA subarray with its own adaptive control loop, so that load values do not have to be copied. However, there are multiple solutions to the nulling problem, and each solution shifts the phase differently at the subarray output. Therefore, maintaining a beam in a desired direction would probably be difficult.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. J. Dinger, "A Planar Version of a 4-GHz Reactively Steered Adaptive Array," IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag., February 1986.
- [2] R. J. Dinger, "Simulation Study of Reactively Steered Adaptive Arrays," Electron. Lett. 21, 383-384 (1985).

FIGURE 1. Block Diagram of Array. Inset shows the configuration for the RESAA subarray with coordinate system.

FIGURE 2. Iso-Power Plot of Adapted Subarray Pattern.

FIGURE 3. Iso-Power Plot of Adapted Primary Array Pattern.

FIGURE 4. Pattern Cuts at Elevation = 0 Degrees. Solid curve, subarray pattern; dashed curve, primary array pattern; dot-dashed curve, primary array pattern with unity element factor.